

Smart Kitchen using Internet of Things

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Abstract - One of the most important rooms in the home is the kitchen. The most important thing to keep in mind while you're moving about the kitchen is the security element. It is critical to identify and address any signs of gas leakage, uncontrolled fire, or abnormally high temperatures without delay. Making a model of a kitchen security system using the Internet of Things is the reason for this investigation. Three different types of sensors and an Arduino UNO are used in the framework's planning. Infrared flame detectors detect fires, temperature sensors keep an eye on things and multi-function gas detectors (MQ-6) detect gas leaks in the kitchen. The Arduino will regulate the transfer when it is linked to the sensor's output. In the event of a gas leak, uncontrolled fire, or excessive temperature increase, the hand-off acts as a fan switch. Arduino will also activate the warning light and the drive, and communicate this information to the worker, when certain criteria are met. The results demonstrate that the framework is capable of functioning in accordance with the optimum decisions.

KEYWORDS:

Arduino UNO, Gas Sensor, Temperature Sensor, Flame Sensor

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the emergence of the IoT has revolutionised human life. An notion behind the Internet of Things (IoT) is the ability for everyday things to communicate with one another [1]. Objects will be able to understand human needs automatically, providing important info regardless of our location, thanks to this capability [2] [3]. People

engage in a variety of physical activities as part of their typical daily lives. One place where people often interact is in the kitchen. As a result of a variety of activities performed in the kitchen, the temperature conditions there will undoubtedly be altered. No matter the temperature, using gas ovens poses a significant risk of fire. Considering the

Moreover, connecting appliances to the internet of things is crucial for maintaining a comfortable temperature in the kitchen and reducing the risk of burns caused by gas stoves. Despite rising prices for most consumer goods, there is a growing movement to find innovative ways to lower prices. This is why the Smart Home project lets customers build and maintain homes that are energy efficient and provide additional digital features. Whether the customer is home or not, a smart house will take advantage of its present situation and provide constant management. You can be certain that your home is maximising its energy efficiency if it has this perk. It is possible to implement this framework and

delve into several design challenges, such as programming, PCB layout, WiFi, TCP/IP standards, Web Server reasoning layout, and alternative arguments. When faced with challenges in programming or equipment planning, this computerization framework provides invaluable pieces of information.

1.1.1 Goal

- 1) To develop a full-fledged automated kitchen system
- 2) To keep an eye on things like temperature, smoke, fire, and LPG gas.

- 3) Gather information using the microcontroller and transmit it to the Internet of Things
- 4) To plan an alert mechanism for when things become worse.

1. LITERATURE SUREVEY

The innovation is transforming every aspect of human existence and is progressing rapidly. In updating the kitchens' materials, experts have put in a lot of time and effort. Everywhere you look, from automated machinery to modified kitchens, something has been shaken up. In order to create a revamped framework that monitors kitchen climate boundaries like light force, room temperature, fire recognition, movement location, and LPG gas level, we have researched and analysed the numerous plans or techniques introduced by analysts concerned with different types of monitoring. We have made an effort in our audit to identify and dissect specifically those programmes or methods where scientists have contributed to the improvement of the current strategies. In order to provide a comprehensive close examination, the survey combines research papers, publications, online sources, and other available material. People who are consistently ahead of the curve expect new gadgets and technologies to make their lives easier. The loop persists despite the pioneers' and analysts' never-ending efforts to find new ways to satisfy people. Despite the widespread availability of the Internet in the 1990s, its use remained limited in the corporate sector due to the poor visibility of its interconnects. In order to provide access to data, the Internet network became the standard for some applications in the 2000s and is now an integral part of many business, consumer, and technological products. Whatever the case may be, these devices are essentially Internet-connected objects that need more human intervention and monitoring via various interfaces and apps. Chef's Table One of the major steps that has

to be rigorously monitored gradually for people's safety, security, and comfort is climate monitoring. New developments in the era of pervasiveness, such as Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) and the Internet, are helping to sort out a passing trend. Systematic management of everyday goods is made possible by the exponential growth of Internet users and developments in online work tools. Customers have received exceptional assurance from web-enabled frameworks. Astute household circumstances have progressed to the point

Everyday household objects and electronics may be rearranged to provide their owners fresh ways to manage them. The development of small-scale, short-distance sensor hubs has been made possible by advancements in computer hardware. They are inexpensive, energy efficient, and may serve several purposes. The feasibility of Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) is influenced by the combined effort of a large number of sensor hubs, which include detecting, information processing, and communication components. Even if there are a lot of researchers taking care of WSN applications, there is still need for research into WSN development and maintenance.

The development and implementation of a smart monitoring and controlling system for kitchen climate has been detailed in this study. A framework that mainly monitors kitchen environmental parameters such as light intensity, room temperature, fire detection, motion detection, and LPG gas level has been developed. The system can monitor the situation in the kitchen and automatically notify a concerned specialist's mobile phone by email or, if necessary, a ready SMS over the GSM network if things start to get out of hand. By sending AT commands to the GSM modem or by performing the basic steps in the client email, which is password protected, the relevant authority may control the system from his mobile phone. Users may monitor and operate transducers using Embedded C-enhanced, dynamic web pages. One area where this structure finds widespread use is in

regions where actual presence is preposterous constantly. The framework offers a total, minimal expense, incredible and easy to use method of constant checking and controller of kitchen. A model is created and tried with high exactness result.

2. BLOCK DIAGRAM

1) Arduino Uno. Ardu

ino Uno is a microcontroller that is as of now famous. Arduino Uno utilizes ATMEGA328 as its microcontroller, has 14 advanced I/O pins and 6 simple sources of info. To program it, the Arduino is associated with the PC utilizing USB type A to type B or what we regularly call the printer link [4].

2) ESP8266.

ESP8266 is a wifi module that serves as a microcontroller enhancement such as Arduino to connect directly to wifi and create TCP / IP connections. This module requires about 3.3v power with three modes of wifi namely Station, Access Point and Both (tools). This module is also

equipped with processor, memory, and GPIO where the number of pins depends on the type of ESP8266 we use. On this

system, This device is used as Wi-Fi shield for Arduino which will connect to Wi-Fi network from available hotspot router. This device will send the collected data from Arduino to the server.

3) Temperature Sensor

LM 35 sends output data in the form of digital output without requiring analog pins. This sensor is very easy to use but has a measurement limit of only up to 60 ° C [5].

4) Gas Leakage Sensor (MQ-6).

Gas sensor MQ-6 is very useful to detect a gas leak in the kitchen. This sensor can detect flammable gases such as LPG, CH₄, CO, Propane to detect smoke from fire. It has a very quick response to gas leakage, but it takes a long time when it first starts up. In this sensor, there is a potentiometer that serves to regulate the sensitivity of the sensor. When the sensor detects a gas leak, the sensor's conductivity will increase depending on the amount of gas concentration detected [6]. In this system, MQ-6 is used to detect leaks on LPG gas.

5) IR Flame Sensor.

In this system, IR flame sensor functions as a fire detector. This sensor will detect fires based on the infrared wave spectrum generated by the fire.

6) Power Supply. This system

uses an adapter that will work on 100 - 240V. The resulting output is 5V, 1A. This power supply will be connected directly to the microcontroller.

3.RESULT

Fig 2 Proteus Simulation Of Our Proposed System

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this system's design and testing allow us to draw the following conclusions:

- All of the sensors in this system are functional, according to the tests. In order to get results that match expectations, calibration is necessary after installation.
- The web and applications may show all gathered data. The effectiveness of the Wi-Fi networks used has a significant impact on the transmission of such data.
- The fan can run correctly in fire and gas leak simulations. There is hope for a warning system. The mobile gadget has the capability to receive email and text messages directly.

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